

Create Report After Running a Snakemake Workflow

Snakemake Hackathon 2025 - Report

1 Create Report After Running a Snakemake Workflow

1.1 Authors

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2 Description

This work was completed as part of the Snakemake Hackathon 2025.

2.0.1 Problem

Previously, generating a Snakemake report required a separate command after the workflow had completed (e.g., `snakemake --report`). This created a two-step process for users who wanted to view a summary of their workflow execution, and could be inconvenient, especially for automated workflows or when the report was immediately needed for analysis.

2.0.2 Solution

This work item introduces the `--report-after-run` command line flag. When specified, this flag automatically generates a Snakemake report immediately after the workflow completes. This streamlines the reporting process and provides users with immediate access to workflow execution summaries.

2.0.3 Code Changes

The key code changes involve:

- Adding the `--report-after-run` flag to the Snakemake argument parser.
- Modifying the workflow execution logic to trigger report generation upon completion if the flag is present.
- Updating the documentation to explain the new flag and its functionality.

2.0.4 Impact

This change improves the user experience by simplifying the process of generating Snakemake reports. It reduces the number of steps required to obtain a workflow summary and makes reporting more convenient for both interactive and automated workflows.

2.1 Acknowledgement

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